

GREEN MARKETING AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AS PREDICTORS OF ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS AMONG SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 10

Pages: 1334-1343

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1934

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12001350

Manuscript Accepted: 05-01-2024

Green Marketing and Corporate Social Responsibility as Predictors of Environmental Awareness among Small and Medium Enterprises

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Abstract

One of the most significant challenges facing stakeholders is the recognition of environmental awareness, particularly in small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The researchers identified the factors influencing environmental awareness among small and medium enterprises in Davao del Norte. The study adopted a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the level of green marketing and corporate social responsibility contributing to environmental awareness. Through stratified random sampling, three hundred respondents were selected. Numeric data were collected using an adapted and validated instrument. The results revealed a very high level of green marketing, as indicated by its components: strategy, internal marketing, product, and marketing presentation. Additionally, the attributes of corporate social responsibility, including corporate governance, corporate commitment, social contribution, and environmental protection, showed a very high level among SME owners. The correlation analysis indicated a significant relationship between green marketing and environmental awareness, as well as between corporate social responsibility and environmental awareness. Regression analysis further demonstrated that both independent variables significantly influence environmental awareness within the SMEs. This suggests that improvements in green marketing and corporate social responsibility lead to a higher level of environmental awareness among SME owners. Furthermore, SMEs can establish programs and events aimed at promoting sustainable practices. Such initiatives not only substantially benefit their business but also demonstrate environmental awareness, leading to a positive contribution to society.

Keywords: *green marketing, corporate social responsibility, environmental awareness*

Introduction

Environmental awareness aids in understanding the aesthetic, biological, and financial significance of protecting the environment. It entails being aware of how human activity affects the environment, including pollution, deforestation, the energy crisis, climate change, and the depletion of natural resources (Daoud et al., 2024; Rai, 2021; Severo et al., 2021). In a recent global study by the World Economic Forum, more than 21,000 adults participated in the survey, with 86% of them expressing a desire for significant change towards a more sustainable world (Broom, 2020). However, when it comes to adopting sustainable management practices, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) frequently lag behind larger firms, restricting their ability to lessen negative social and environmental effects. One significant issue is that fewer SMEs have sustainability goals and less experience in environmental management (Howell, 2023; Ibrahim, 2023; Moursellas et al., 2023).

As stated by Hasan (2018), while people generally recognize the environmental and social impact of SMEs, most have little knowledge of the actual effects, with many SMEs even viewing environmental issues as unrelated to them. This sentiment is supported by Malesios et al. (2023), who found that SMEs prioritize economic performance over environmental and social factors to remain competitive in the market. Consequently, the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) reiterates that environmental awareness is an indispensable tool for sustainable development. Given the vast number of SMEs and their significant contribution to the economy, there is a clear need for further study to investigate environmental awareness from their perspective. Cheang et al. (2019) also emphasize that as environmental issues become increasingly pressing worldwide, there is a growing imperative to address these issues and promote pro-environmental behavior as a means of achieving sustainability goals.

In the United States, there are approximately 28 million SMEs, constituting over 60% of the nation's total employment (Ashton et al., 2018). Despite the perception that SMEs may have lower individual environmental footprints compared to larger counterparts, Purwandani and Michaud (2021) elucidate that their cumulative impacts can surpass those of many large businesses. This underscores a significant environmental challenge stemming from SMEs. In Greece, SMEs grapple with enhancing their efficiency in waste management and disposal, with the average yearly waste reduction rate consistently below 10% (Moursellas et al., 2022). Similarly, in Malaysia, the Sabah state faces alarming weather changes, prompting urgent environmental awareness initiatives within SMEs (Suriashah, 2021). These disparate challenges across different municipalities highlight the pressing need for concerted efforts to address environmental sustainability within the SME sector globally.

Based on the data provided from the 2022 Last of Establishments (LE) report by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), approximately 99.59% of establishments in the Philippines are micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs). Among these, small enterprises comprise 8.69% (96,464), while medium enterprises constitute 0.40% (4,484) of the total establishments. Meanwhile, Nasserddine (2024) highlighted a staggering statistic revealing that the annual production of plastic garbage equals the weight of the entire global population, with 79% of this waste ending up in landfills or the environment. This issue is particularly pressing in Baguio

City, where environmental problems persist, including climate change impacts, land degradation, biodiversity loss, and widespread pollution of soil, air, and water. These environmental challenges are often exacerbated by a lack of awareness and sustainable practices (Altarez, 2020).

In Davao City, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) grapple with an alarming environmental waste crisis, particularly evident in the city's sanitary landfill situated in Barangay New Carmen. According to Cortez (2023), the landfill has far surpassed its capacity, accumulating nearly 1 million tons of garbage since 2016. This overflow exacerbates existing environmental concerns and poses significant health risks to both residents and ecosystems. Furthermore, Alam (2018) highlights another pressing issue across the Philippines, particularly in Metro Manila, where the proliferation of electronic gadgets coupled with their improper disposal practices has resulted in a staggering electronic waste management dilemma. The inadequate handling of e-waste not only exposes individuals to hazardous substances but also jeopardizes environmental integrity. The repercussions of such negligence are profound, endangering both human well-being and ecological sustainability.

While the link between corporate practices and environmental awareness has been extensively acknowledged, Chaudhary (2020) argued that any comprehensive examination of how green corporate practices influence organizational performance remains incomplete without a thorough consideration of their underlying processes. Recent studies have underscored a significant gap in research regarding the mechanisms through which green corporate practices translate into environmental awareness (Pham et al., 2020). Furthermore, the researchers have not found any local studies about this matter. Jabbour (2019) has highlighted the dearth of in-depth investigations into the relationships between green corporate practices and various related factors, such as green marketing, green human capital, the roles of intermediaries, and the interplay among different green corporate practices in shaping organizational performance.

The study's social relevance extends beyond academia to address pressing contemporary issues within the business sector. In today's rapidly evolving landscape, where environmental concerns are at the forefront of global discourse, understanding the factors that influence environmental awareness among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is paramount. By investigating the roles of green marketing and corporate social responsibility (CSR) as predictors of environmental awareness, the research provides actionable insights for SMEs seeking to adopt sustainable practices. Moreover, by disseminating these findings through presentations at research forums and publications in relevant journals, the study serves as a valuable resource for policymakers and business leaders alike. It not only contributes to academic discourse but also empowers stakeholders with the knowledge needed to implement effective strategies for promoting environmental consciousness and fostering sustainable development within SMEs. In essence, the research bridges the gap between theory and practice, offering tangible solutions to address the urgent need for environmentally responsible business practices in today's competitive market environment.

Research Questions

This study aims to quantify the effectiveness of green marketing and corporate social responsibility towards environmental awareness in the SME sector of Davao Del Norte. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What was the level of green marketing in terms of:
 - 1.1. strategy;
 - 1.2. internal marketing;
 - 1.3. product; and
 - 1.4. marketing communication?
2. What was the level of Corporate Social Responsibility in terms of?
 - 2.1. corporate governance;
 - 2.2. corporate commitments;
 - 2.3. social contribution; and
 - 2.4. environmental protection?
3. What was the level of environmental awareness in terms of:
 - 3.1. attitudes;
 - 3.2. subjectivity norms; and
 - 3.3. perceived behavioral controls?
4. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. Green marketing and environmental awareness of the SME's of Santo Tomas?
 - 4.2. Corporate Social Responsibility and environmental awareness of the SME's of Santo Tomas?
5. Do green marketing and corporate social responsibility significantly influence the environmental awareness of SMEs?

Literature Review

Green Marketing Influence on Environmental Awareness

Several studies found that consumers also perceived that green marketing practices developed by companies gained their attention on the preservation of the natural environment businesses and began to modify the behavior of company stakeholders to overcome social,

ethical, and environmental sustainability problems (Galindo-Martín et al., 2020; Guo et al., 2020). The business strategy developed by the company was also quickly accepted and then adapted to the environmental management system, minimized waste, and integrated environmental issues such as voluntary environmental programs and mandatory regulations, and corporate green innovation (Li et al., 2020). The influence of a green competitive advantage on green marketing performance was good. The results support previous studies stating that green marketing performance depends on green innovation (Sudaryati et al., 2020).

Corporate Social Responsibility

The concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has garnered considerable interest in scholarly works because of its implications for stakeholder interactions, business performance, and social and environmental issues. A multitude of academics has made contributions to the definitions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and its diverse aspects. For instance, Le, T. T. (2023) defines CSR as a company's responsibility to the community, the environment, and its stakeholders by achieving a balance between corporate interests, stakeholder concerns, and social and environmental issues. Jintao et al. (2020) further elaborate on the diverse stakeholder groups impacted by CSR initiatives, highlighting their relevance for firm competitiveness. Similarly, Le (2023) stated that, the expectations that various stakeholder groups have of an organization vary and are used as benchmarks for CSR success. As a result, employees anticipated things like a safe workplace, appropriate working hours, a living wage, a nondiscriminatory policy, professional growth opportunities, and more.

CSR Influence on Environmental Awareness

According to Jintao et al. (2020), Businesses are anticipated to utilize resources efficiently and protect the environment. Hence, businesses that practice social responsibility often form alliances with companies that uphold environmental and social concerns. As a result, the organization's reputation was improved, and professional networks were formed so that people could exchange ideas and work together to accomplish the intended goals.

Subsequently, the conservation of the environment is a major concern for today's businesses, which must achieve a balance between operations that respect the environment and economic growth. Tai and Chuang (2014) emphasize that enterprises should be more than just profitable tools; they should also serve as responsible citizens.

Environmental Awareness

Rai (2021) stated that environmental awareness was a recognition and understanding of the natural world. It includes understanding the environmental consequences of human actions such as pollution, deforestation, energy crisis, climate change, and destruction of natural resources. Environmental awareness motivates people and societies to take proactive measures to safeguard and preserve the environment for future generations.

Furthermore, in the study of Xu et al. (2019), environmental awareness was crucial in shaping consumer preferences toward sustainable products. In This scenario, companies that adopt sustainable practices can gain competitive advantages by meeting the demand of increasingly environmentally conscious consumers (Severo et al., 2021). Moreover, in the study of Sallirosas (2023), this awareness can help them to offer products that align with the values and preferences of their target customers and ultimately enhance their profitability.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher employed a quantitative methodology that primarily draws on natural scientific approaches to generate hard facts and numerical data. It uses statistical, computational, and mathematical techniques to establish a cause-and-effect link between two variables (Ahmad et al., 2019). The quantitative approach was helpful for researchers who want to give strong proof and a solid foundation for the findings of their investigation.

Additionally, the descriptive correlation method was used to conduct the statistical analysis of the collected data. The goal of this was to gather data in order to methodically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon (Lord, 2000). Therefore, researchers were able to determine the relationship or contrast between the independent and dependent variables at the conclusion of the investigation.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the SME owners and managers in charge of the small and medium enterprises around the municipalities of Davao Del Norte. An estimated 300 participants were selected through a stratified random sampling method. As reported by the Socio-Economic Profiling System, Davao del Norte comprises eight municipalities and three cities in total. Collectively, the SMEs have a total number of 1,432 establishments in total and were conducted in the eight municipalities of Davao del Norte. Specifically, Municipal A consisted of 41 respondents, Municipal B consisted of 28 respondents, Municipal C consisted of 71 respondents, Municipal D consisted of 60 respondents, Municipal E consisted of 15 respondents, Municipal F consisted of 13, Municipal G consisted of 66, and Municipal H consisted of 10 respondents. Moreover, this study utilized a strategic sampling technique to determine the final total number of respondents. Using the Raosoft online sample size calculator with a 95% confidence level (Z-

Score = 1.96) and a 5% margin of error, the optimal sample size for this quantitative study was 304 SMEs, taking into account the identified collective population size of 1432.

Table 1 below shows the sample size of the SMEs in different municipalities in Davao del Norte.

Table 1. *Distribution of the respondents*

<i>SME</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Sample</i>
Municipality A	192	13.41%	41
Municipality B	133	9.29%	28
Municipality C	332	23.18%	71
Municipality D	282	19.70%	60
Municipality E	72	5.02%	15
Municipality F	63	4.40%	13
Municipality G	312	21.79%	66
Municipality H	46	3.21%	10
Total	1432	100%	304

Instruments

Green Marketing

The instrument for the independent variable was adapted from the Measuring green marketing: scale development and validation questionnaire (Vilkaite-vaitone et al., 2022). The green marketing contained a total of 15 items. Strategy (3 items), Internal Marketing (3 items), Product (3 items), and Marketing Communication (3 items).

Furthermore, this questionnaire was anchored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 5- Strongly Agree, 4- Agree, 3- Moderately Agree, 2- Disagree, and 1- Strongly Disagree. The following parameter limits, with their corresponding descriptions, were applied to the level of green marketing.

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Very High	This indicates that Green Marketing was always manifested.
4	3.40-4.19	High	This indicates that Green Marketing was oftentimes manifested.
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This indicates that Green Marketing was sometimes manifested.
2	1.80-2.59	Low	This indicates that Green Marketing was rarely manifested.
1	1.00-1.79	Very Low	This indicates that Green Marketing was the least manifested.

Corporate Social Responsibility

The instrument for the second independent variable was adapted from this survey questionnaire was adopted from a Corporate Social Responsibility (Fang-Mei Tai 2014; Shu-Hao Chuang, 2014) study on the dimensions of Corporate Social Responsibility. The modified questionnaire contained a total of 21 items with 3 questions per 4 indicators. Corporate Governance (3 items); Corporate Commitment (3 items) Social Contribution (3 items); and Environmental Protection (3).

The five-point Likert scale to be used for the Corporate and Social Responsibility variable was as follows:

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Very High	This indicates that Corporate Social Responsibility is always manifested.
4	3.40-4.19	High	This indicates that Corporate Social Responsibility was oftentimes manifested.
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This indicates that Corporate Social Responsibility was sometimes manifested.
2	1.80-2.59	Low	This indicates that Corporate Social Responsibility was rarely manifested.
1	1.00-1.79	Very Low	This indicates that corporate Social Responsibility was least manifested.

Environmental Awareness.

The instrument for the dependent variable was adopted from the Measuring Consumers' environmental awareness: development of constructs and measurement scale items questionnaire (Madhusanka et al., 2022). The environmental awareness contained a total of 9 items. Attitude (3 items), Subject norms (3 items), and Perceived Behavioral Controls (3 items).

Moreover, this questionnaire was anchored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 5- Strongly Agree, 4- Agree, 3- Moderately Agree, 2- Disagree, and 1- Strongly Disagree. The following parameter limits, with their corresponding descriptions, were applied to the level of environmental awareness.

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5	4.20-5.00	Very High	This indicates that Environmental Awareness is always evident
4	3.40-4.19	High	This indicates that Environmental Awareness is oftentimes evident
3	2.60-3.39	Average	This indicates that Environmental Awareness is sometimes evident
2	1.80-2.59	Low	This indicates that Environmental Awareness is rarely evident
1	1.00-1.79	Very Low	This indicates that Environmental Awareness is least evident.

Procedure

To initiate the data collection process, the researchers sought approval from the research office and the Department Chairman of Bachelor of Science in Office Administration. The researchers then obtained a letter of approval from the ethics committee after submitting a formal permission letter to conduct the study.

In ensuring the questionnaire's validity, the researchers engaged evaluators to review and validate it during the data collection phase. Following established procedures, the researchers employed a survey questionnaire methodology. In the distribution of the questionnaire, the respondents received a letter from the researchers asking for their cooperation in answering the questionnaire. The researchers introduced themselves to the respondents, stated the name of their study, and described its objectives. The questionnaire was personally distributed and collected by the researchers after the time given for them to do so.

The researcher gathered and totaled the data for analysis after the survey respondents provided their responses. In tabulation of data, the researchers asked a statistician to help in determining the appropriate statistical tools to be used and in interpreting the data. In light of the results, the researcher formulated conclusions and recommendations for this study.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tool was used in the computation of data and testing the hypotheses at the alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Mean. The mean, which was also known as the average, was the total sum of values in a sample divided by the number of values in the sample (Hurley & Tenny, 2023).

Standard Deviation. This tool was used; hence it was the descriptive statistic that estimates the scatter of values around the sample mean (Andrade, 2020).

Pearson r. This tool was utilized for the purpose of measuring the strength and direction of association that exists between two variables measured on at least an interval scale. A Pearson's correlation attempts to draw a line of best fit through the data of two variables, and the Pearson's correlation coefficient, r , indicates how far away all these data points are from this line of best fit (Obilor & Amadi, 2018).

Multiple Regression Analysis was used to examine the relationship between a dependent variable and two or more independent variables. It allows researchers to assess how changes in the independent variables are associated with changes in the dependent variable while controlling for the effects of other variables.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

This section presents the results and discussions of the study. In particular, this shows the data in tables and its corresponding descriptive interpretations.

Summary of level of green marketing of Small and Medium Enterprises

Table 2 summarizes the level of green marketing of owners and managers of SMEs. Among the four indicators, strategy got the highest mean of 4.95 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. It was followed by a product with a mean of 4.82, a descriptive equivalent of high. Next to product was marketing communication with a mean of 4.75. On the other hand, internal marketing got the lowest mean of 4.69 still has a descriptive equivalent of very high.

Table 2. Summary of level of green marketing of Small and Medium Enterprises

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Strategy	0.27	4.95	Very High
2. Internal Marketing	0.54	4.69	Very High
3. Product	0.36	4.82	Very High
4. Marketing Communication	0.52	4.75	Very High
Category	0.42	4.80	Very High

The level of green marketing of owners and managers has an overall mean of 4.80 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the level of green marketing was much more evident. The standard deviation of 0.42 in the overall mean indicates that there is some degree of variability or spread in the data. Some owners and managers may have rated the level of green marketing higher or lower than the mean, contributing to this dispersion.

The results above show a generally positive perception of green marketing practices among SME owners and managers. The findings are supported by the study of Bruno and Tadeo (2023) stating that Green marketing practices in micro and small enterprises (MSEs) can contribute to sustainable internal business operations and corporate social responsibilities. As SMEs implement various green marketing strategies, such as providing safe products and services, implementing environment-friendly pollution prevention methods,

and advertising green awareness, these practices have been found to be highly effective in production, packaging, advertising, and operation, but less effective in distribution. Green Marketing has become increasingly important and gained wide acceptance within the business world as a viable competitive strategy and strengthening the brand image of the business. It improves both business reputation and performance (Nguyen et al 2020; Mukonza & Swarts, 2020; Sugandini, 2020).

Summary of the level of Corporate Social Responsibility attributes

Table 3 summarizes the level of corporate social responsibility of owners and managers of SMEs. Among the four indicators, environmental protection got the highest mean of 4.92 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. It was followed by social contribution with a mean of 4.84, a descriptive equivalent of high. Next to social contribution was corporate commitment with a mean of 4.79. On the other hand, corporate governance got the lowest mean of 4.59 still has a descriptive equivalent of very high. The standard deviations (SD) for each indicator are low, ranging from 0.22 to 0.60. This suggests that owners and managers of SMEs have a consistent perception of the level of CSR across the various indicators.

Table 3. Summary of the level of Corporate Social Responsibility attributes

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Corporate Governance	0.60	4.59	Very High
2. Corporate Commitment	0.39	4.79	Very High
3. Social Contribution	0.39	4.84	Very High
4. Environmental Protection	0.22	4.92	Very High
Category	0.40	4.79	Very High

The data indicate that owners and managers of SMEs place a high importance on CSR, particularly in terms of environmental protection and social contribution. While there is a strong commitment to CSR overall, there may be opportunities for SMEs to further enhance their corporate governance practices. The findings are supported by the study of Lajara et al. (2022) CSR is important as it represents the voluntary commitment of companies to behave responsibly with the environment and consider economic, environmental, and social issues in their decision-making process. Moreover, Siam et al. (2019) emphasized that Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is one of the key aspects in increasing customer satisfaction. It is a component of business elements economic, legal, and moral activities aimed at fulfilling corporate and societal goals. Moreover, corporate social responsibility has become a key point of sustainability and its concept has received higher attention from academics and practitioners. Its implementation is a way for businesses to benefit themselves while being accountable for their effects on society and the environment caused by business activities (Soojeen et al., 2019; Yuan et al, 2020; Coyle et al. 2019).

Summary of level of environmental awareness

Table 4 summarizes the level of environmental awareness of owners and managers of SMEs. Among the four indicators, perceived behavioral controls got the highest mean of 4.88 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. It was followed by subjective norms with a mean of 4.80, a descriptive equivalent of high. On the other hand, attitude got the lowest mean of 4.70 and still has a descriptive equivalent of very high.

Table 4. Summary of level of environmental awareness

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Attitude	0.64	4.70	Very High
2. Subjectivity Norms	0.50	4.80	Very High
3. Perceived Behavioral Controls	0.40	4.88	Very High
Category	0.51	4.79	Very High

The findings indicate that SMEs' owners and managers have a generally high level of environmental awareness, with a strong sense of behavioral control over their environmental activities and knowledge of the influence of subjective norms. Overall, the findings show a positive attitude toward environmental sustainability among SMEs.

The result is supported by the works of Lukacs et al. (2023) emphasizing that Environmental awareness has an important part in purchasing decisions. Consumers are increasingly attempting to limit their environmental impact and make ecologically mindful choices. Research indicates that customers' environmental awareness favorably impacts their green purchases as cited by Mahmoud et.al, (2023). Consumers may select environmental measures with less commitment and sacrifice. Overall, consumers' environmental knowledge plays an important role in molding their purchase decisions and fostering sustainable consumption. Identifying environmental cognition, subjective norms, and self-efficacy have a highly significant positive impact on green purchase intention, with self-efficacy being the best predictor. It contributes to decision-making recommendations for promoting green consumption and highlights the importance of emotional factors, such as environmental indebtedness, in shaping consumer behavior (Yu et al., 2022; Bansal & Agarwal 2022; Lin et al., 2021).

Significance of the relationship between green marketing, corporate social responsibility, and environmental awareness

Table 5 shows the relationship between green marketing, corporate social responsibility, and environmental awareness among SMEs.

Table 5. Significance of the Relationship Between the Variables

Variables Correlated	r	p-value	Decision on Ho	Decision on Relationship
Green Marketing & Environmental Awareness	0.585	0.000	Reject	Significant
Corporate Social Responsibility & Environmental Awareness	0.552	0.000	Reject	Significant

There exists a significant positive correlation between green marketing and environmental awareness among SMEs ($p < 0.000$), as evidenced by an r-value of 0.585 with a moderate positive correlation and the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that as the level of green marketing increases, so does the level of environmental awareness. In simpler terms, SMEs engaging in more green marketing activities tend to exhibit higher levels of environmental awareness.

The findings, supported by Škataric et al. (2021), underscore the pivotal role of green marketing, contending that its adoption not only confers a competitive advantage but also fosters increased profitability for businesses, all the while bolstering environmental conservation efforts. The adoption and effective implementation of green marketing initiatives present a unique opportunity for companies to actively engage in environmental preservation, thereby aligning societal and profit objectives. This symbiotic relationship between environmental stewardship and economic prosperity is underscored by previous studies (Nacka et al., 2019). Furthermore, Širola and Rosandić's (2019) survey in Croatia reveals a significant correlation between awareness of environmental protection and the propensity to purchase and utilize eco-friendly products and services. Consequently, green marketing serves as a catalyst for heightening consumer awareness regarding the positive environmental impact of their consumption choices.

Similarly, there is a significant positive correlation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental awareness among SMEs ($p > 0.000$) with an r-value of 0.552 with a moderate positive correlation and the rejection of the null hypotheses. This indicates that as the level of CSR increases, the level of environmental awareness also tends to increase. SMEs that prioritize CSR initiatives are likely to have higher levels of environmental awareness.

The findings, as corroborated by Škataric et al. (2021), underscore the pivotal role of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in organizations, encapsulating a commitment to societal and environmental well-being within their operational frameworks. Social responsibility encompasses investments in human capital, environmental stewardship, consumer engagement, and adherence to legal obligations. Notably, the statistical significance of the two variables, as indicated by a p-value below 0.05, underscores their substantive relevance. Specifically, the study reveals a positive correlation between CSR practices and green marketing initiatives with heightened environmental awareness among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). This implies that SMEs prioritizing sustainability in both marketing strategies and CSR endeavors are more inclined to cultivate heightened environmental consciousness within their organizational ecosystems and among their stakeholders.

Regression Analysis on the Environmental Awareness of Owners and Managers of SMEs as Influenced by Green Marketing and Corporate Social Responsibility

Regression analysis was conducted to ascertain the substantial impact of green marketing and corporate social responsibility on the environmental awareness of owners and managers. The outcomes, delineated in Table 5, unveiled that green marketing emerges as a statistically significant predictor of environmental awareness ($p > 0.05$).

Table 6. Regression Analysis on the Environmental Awareness of Owners and Managers of SMEs as Influenced by Green Marketing and Corporate Social Responsibility

Independent Variable with indicators	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-stat	p-value	Decision@ $\alpha = 0.05$
	B	Standard Error				
(Constant)	-.107	0.325				
Green Marketing	0.599	0.093	0.390	6.474	0.000	Rejected
Corporate Social Responsibility	0.414	0.092	0.270	4.487	0.000	Rejected
Dependent Variable: Environmental Awareness						
F-ratio: 109.465			Adjusted R Square: 0.378			

The results indicate that both green marketing and CSR positively and significantly influence the environmental awareness of SMEs owners and managers. The findings are supported by the idea that by incorporating environmental messaging and sustainable practices into their marketing strategies, companies can contribute to shaping consumer attitudes and behaviors towards more environmentally responsible choices. (Lajevardi et al., 2021) Specifically, for every one-unit increase in green marketing, environmental awareness increases by approximately 0.599 units, and for every one-unit increase in CSR, environmental awareness increases by approximately 0.414 units. These coefficients were accompanied by high t-statistics and extremely low p-values (both $p < 0.05$), suggesting strong statistical significance. This is further confirmed by data indicating that green marketing and social corporate responsibility are drivers for companies to create beneficial social and environmental impacts. (Lopez & Smith, 2020; Nematollah & Sadeghi, 2022) Consumer demand for responsible products and services can encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices. The standardized coefficients (Beta) further confirm the relative strength of these relationships after accounting for the scale of measurement, with green marketing

showing a Beta of 0.390 and CSR showing a Beta of 0.270.

These results collectively demonstrate that SMEs engaging in green marketing strategies and demonstrating strong CSR practices tend to exhibit higher levels of environmental awareness among their stakeholders. Furthermore, the overall regression model demonstrated a significant fit, with the F-ratio indicating statistical significance and the Adjusted R Square revealing that green marketing and CSR as independent variables explain approximately 37.8% of the variance in environmental awareness. This shows that, while green marketing and CSR play important roles in molding environmental awareness, other factors not included in the model may also contribute to SMEs' environmental consciousness. Nonetheless, these findings highlight the importance of incorporating sustainability initiatives, such as green marketing and CSR, into SMEs' business strategies not only to raise environmental awareness but also to foster an environmental culture and contribute to the larger goals of sustainable development. Furthermore, this is supported by the works of Hasudungan and Saragih (2023), which attested that there had been a lot of emphasis from several studies that green marketing and social corporate responsibility have significant effects on environmental awareness.

Conclusion

The study's findings unveil several key insights regarding the levels of green marketing, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and environmental awareness among owners and managers of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Notably, strategy emerges as the highest-rated aspect of green marketing, followed closely by product and marketing communication, while internal marketing lags slightly behind but still registers a very high score. Similarly, in the realm of CSR, environmental protection garners the highest rating, trailed by social contribution and corporate commitment, with corporate governance receiving the lowest mean score but still classified as very high. Moreover, concerning environmental awareness, perceived behavioral controls and subjectivity norms rank highest, while attitude scores slightly lower but still maintains a very high descriptive equivalent. Additionally, the study establishes significant relationships between environmental awareness and both green marketing and CSR among SME owners and managers, with moderate positive correlations and p-values below the 0.05 significance level, leading to the rejection of null hypotheses. Furthermore, the influence of green marketing and CSR on environmental awareness is underscored by their significant beta coefficients and p-values, affirming the rejection of null hypotheses. These findings collectively underscore the importance of fostering environmental awareness and integrating green marketing and CSR practices within SMEs to promote sustainability and environmental stewardship.

Based on the findings, analysis, and conclusions drawn in the study, several recommendations emerge for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) aiming to bolster their green marketing and corporate social responsibility efforts. Firstly, addressing the evident gap in internal marketing, SMEs should prioritize enhancing internal communication and engagement regarding environmental activities. This could involve instituting training programs, workshops, and regular communication channels to educate staff about sustainability's value and involve them in green initiatives. Secondly, given the identified deficiency in corporate governance, SMEs should concentrate on fortifying their governance structures to better address environmental and social concerns. This may entail reviewing and updating corporate policies, setting clear environmental objectives and targets, and appointing responsible individuals or committees to oversee sustainability initiatives. Thirdly, SMEs should emphasize environmental awareness initiatives to elevate the lower mean attitude score. These programs should educate stakeholders on environmental conservation's importance, the impact of their actions on the environment, and the benefits of implementing sustainable practices. Furthermore, regular activities should be held to ensure continuous learning and reinforcement of environmental principles within the firm. By enhancing environmental literacy and awareness among owners, managers, and employees, SMEs can cultivate a more environmentally conscientious workforce and facilitate sustainable practices' integration into their operations.

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